

CLASSIFICATION SCHEME OF COMPONENTS OF THE CHARGE OF MELTED FLUXES FOR AUTOMATIC ARC WELDING

Khudoyorov S.S., associate professor, PhD
Tashkent State Technical University

Welding production is one of the leading industries, thanks to which more than half of the gross national product of industrially developed countries is produced. The determining factor in the quality of a weld is the correct selection of welding materials and raw materials for their production. General principles for selecting welding wire and flux for automatic arc welding are determined by the following conditions [1,2]:

- a certain complex and level of mechanical properties of the weld metal in combination with the metal of the welded parts;
- absence of pores and slag inclusions or their minimum sizes and quantity per unit of weld length, acceptable for specific products or operating conditions;
- obtaining a set of special properties of the weld metal;
- absence of hot and cold cracks;
- satisfactory sanitary and hygienic characteristics of welding materials.

The fulfillment of the specified conditions is achieved by the appropriate selection of welding wire and components included in the composition of the fused flux. Modern fused fluxes are complex multi-component systems.

The materials included in them perform various metallurgical and technological functions. Traditional components of welding fused fluxes have heterogeneity of charge particles by fraction, by morphology, by fusibility and viscosity during melting, which does not allow achieving the required parameters of arc combustion stability, slag and gas function [1,2].

For the production of fused fluxes for arc welding, a raw material base is used, which is conventionally divided into: mineral raw materials, ferroalloys and artificial chemical materials. The initial analysis of the components of the charge for the production of fused flux is carried out according to the developed classification [3].

The components of the charge for the production of fused flux are divided into:

1) Ferroalloys:

- ferroboration;
- ferrovandium;
- ferromolybdenum;
- ferrochrome;
- ferroaluminum;
- ferrotitanium;
- ferrosilicon;
- ferromanganese;

2) Mineral raw materials:

- carbonates;
- titanium-containing substances;
- aluminosilicates;
- fluorine-containing raw materials;
- silicates;
- quartz materials;
- iron and manganese ores;

3) Artificially obtained materials:

- fluorine-containing materials;
- chlorine-containing materials;
- carbonates;
- oxides.

The use of ultra-dispersed components in the composition of welding materials can contribute to the formation of optimal structures of fused fluxes, which will ensure more efficient use of the components of welding materials. One of the tasks solved in this work is the introduction of small quantities of alloying elements into the components of welding materials to improve the welding and technological characteristics of the seam. In this case, the distribution of these elements should be as uniform as possible throughout the entire volume of the batch of fused flux. In practice, it was not possible to achieve such a distribution by introducing small additives of the necessary elements directly into the composition of the fused flux; therefore, the transition into the composition of the weld metal is also uneven. The developed composition of the fused flux contains, wt. %: marble – 15,0–17,5, quartz sand – 40,4–46,8, fluorspar – 8,3–10,4, enriched kaolin – 8,8–12,4, ferrosilicon manganese – 19,9–20,1.

Literature

1. Кузнецов М.А. Нанотехнологии и наноматериалы в сварочном производстве (Обзор) - Сварочное производство. – 2010. – №12. – С.23–26.
2. Адкина Ю.В., Николаев А.И., Петров В.Б., Путинцев Н.М. Легирующие элементы в минеральных и синтетических компонентах сварочных материалов - Прикладная химия. 2016. – Т.83, №12. – С. 1960– 1964.